

IMPACT OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS IN ACCESS TO HIGHER EDUCATION AMONG SCHEDULED CASTES IN UTTAR PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

Indian caste system is based on highly unequal elements of socio-economic factors which also affect the accessibility to higher education among the scheduled castes. The present paper is an attempt to analyze the impact of socio-economic factors on accessibility to higher education among SCs. The study is based on quantitative work of primary data surveyed from three districts of Uttar Pradesh namely, Faizabad, Sonbhadra and Lucknow. Analysis reveals that income is most important factor which is directly or indirectly related to other factors in order to promote accessibility to higher education among SCs. Moreover, early marriage, lack of educational resource and facilities, illiteracy or low level of parental education, larger household size and earning while learning have negative impact on accessibility to higher education.

Keywords: Accessibility to Higher-Education, Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER), Higher-Education, Scheduled Castes, Socio-Economic Factors.

Introduction

Scheduled Castes (SCs) is considered as a most backward community in the Indian society. In the context of Indian society, the parameters of gender, caste, class and religion are crucial factors in access to higher education. In spite of implementation of several government schemes and programmes to facilitate 'equality of opportunity', it has failed to eliminate the embedded nature of discrimination, disadvantage, and the structural relations and internalized structures of inequality in the society (Vasavi, 2012). Total gross enrolment ratio in higher education is 20.4 percent for 18-23 years of age group, while it is only 12.5 percent for the SCs population (MHRD, 2013). Further, the number of SCs students who actually graduate from higher education is only 4.19 percent of the total SCs student enrolled in higher education in 2000 (Thorat, 2006). Dropout rates in higher education, especially among disadvantaged groups such as SCs and STs are higher than the national average (OECD (2014)). The SCs, thus, are still lagging behind when compared to their counterpart (Non-Scheduled population) when it comes to the proportion enrolled in higher education. The study is based on the quantitative work of primary data of a total of 504 samples surveyed from households in three districts of Uttar Pradesh namely, Faizabad, Sonbhadra and Lucknow. Thus to understand the cause of backwardness of SCs in higher education, the present paper analyzes the socio-economic characteristics of SCs students aged between 18 -23 year who are out of higher education system and those who have access to higher education. It has been found that social and economic background of the SCs greatly influences access to higher education directly whereas a few others bear upon it indirectly.

Overview of Literature

Historically, SCs were engaged in menial and defiling occupations and were characterised by widespread illiteracy, mass unemployment, low income, low technology and scarcity of resources (Sinha, 1981). The poor performance and access to higher education among SCs are mainly because of poor socio-economic background and lower quality of primary and secondary schools which SCs students have access to in comparison to other student's (Velaskar, 1986). Main reason for SCs drop out from college is failure in exams; but almost as significant was a need to find employment in order to provide financial support for oneself and one's family (Aikara, 1980). The poor schooling facilities, poverty and lack of economic resources are the important factors for SCs drop out in higher education. The women are especially subject to the social prejudices in the rural areas. The lack of financial help and incentives at the early age are the other main reasons (Chanana, 1993). SCs students hail from a less privileged socio-economic background and lack of parental education, it has attributed to higher dropout rate in higher education (Weisskopf, 2004). High dropout arises out of a compulsion for employment to feed and support the family among SCs. Other constraints like caste based discrimination, malpractice by teachers, socio-cultural norms and tradition, policies for welfare of society, etc. also affects the access to higher education among SCs (Aikara, 1980). Thus, SCs in the higher education today is still deprived. This is mainly because of lack of access and availability of higher education, which has to be linked with the socio-economic environment.

Research Methodology

The basic question for the study is that "How the social and economic factors affect to access the higher education for SCs"? In this regard, the paper is based on 504 samples which had been collected through primary household survey from three districts of Uttar Pradesh namely, Faizabad, Sonbhadra and Lucknow with 166, 166 and 172 respectively. Besides, secondary data also have been extracted from Census of India 2001 for computing Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) (Sinha, 2008) for SCs in the study area in order to supplement the analysis. To understand the socio-economic characteristics of SCs, a simple percentage has been calculated for the analysis.

Scheduled Castes in Higher Education

Uttar Pradesh constitutes 16.50 percent of the total population of India, whereas it contains 20.53 percent of the total SCs population of the country (Census of India, 2011).

SL	District	Persons	Males	Females
1	Faizabad	6.16%	9.71%	2.57%
2	Lucknow	11.06%	13.42%	8.05%
3	Sonbhadra	3.66%	5.76%	1.56%
4	Uttar Pradesh	7.74%	11.00%	3.77%

Source: Computed from Census of India 2001, C-Series Tables

Further, Uttar Pradesh has 20.70percent SCs population. Out of the total SC population, 86.28percent lives in rural areas whereas 13.71percent lives in urban areas. Gross enrollment ratio in higher education among SCs is only 7.74percent while it is 13.29percent for non-Scheduled Caste students in Uttar Pradesh. The surveyed districts i.e. Faizabad, Sonbhadra and Lucknow records 6percent, 11percent and 3.6percent GER among SCs respectively. District Lucknow is better than rest of the two surveyed districts. Sonbhadra records worst in GER for male as well as female among SCs.

Analysis of Primary Data Results

Status of Higher Education among the SCs

Data result shows that 25percent of the total respondents were eligible to enrol in higher education; unfortunately they did not join the higher education due to some problem. Further, about 15percent of the students had discontinued their higher education before obtaining the degree. On the other hand, 36 percent of the total respondents were pursuing higher education, while 23percent students had obtained their degrees. Thus, it is clear that 40percent students were out of the higher education system and 60percent were in the higher education among the total surveyed respondents.

Figure-1

Source: Computed from Household Field Work Data, 2011, (HE=Higher Education)

The result reveals that Faizabad district records highest proportion (48percent) of students who were attending some institution of higher education. A significant proportion (24percent) had completed their graduation also. In this district, the percentage of respondents who had discontinued their education after higher secondary school (12th) was 16percent of the total. The trends in Sonbhadra district also reveal that about 18percent of the respondents had completed their graduation and about one fourth (24percent) of them were pursuing higher education. The worrying trend is the high proportion (40percent) of those who had discontinued their higher education. Similarly, Lucknow district also has a high proportion (36percent) of respondents pursuing higher education, followed by those who had already completed 29percent their graduation. This district also has significant proportion (33percent) of respondents who have drop out from higher education (Appendix-1).

Gender

Concerning the gender of respondents, male students were higher in proportion (56percent) enrolled in higher education in comparison to female students, i.e. female students were lagging behind in enrollment (44.40percent) of higher education to their counterpart (Appendix-2a).

Marital Status

A significant proportion (58percent) of respondents was reported unmarried, while 42percent of the total respondents were married during their higher education. In terms of age at effective marriage, there were 33percent students who got married between the ages of 18 to 24 years. A small proportion (9percent) of students was also reported as having married before 18 years of age (Appendix-2a).

Household Size

In case of household size, only 5.4percent of the total surveyed households have ideal size (4 members) of the family. Household size with 7-10 members' families constituted highest proportion (44percent) of the total surveyed households. The family size of 5-6 members constitutes 28.80percent and biggest family size (> 11 members) shares 22.10 percent of the total surveyed families (Appendix-2b).

Parental Education

Appendix-2c shows that a majority of the respondents' father (36percent) and Mother (86percent) were illiterate. If we consider father's education then it comes out that more than half (66percent) of the total respondents' fathers were below high school level of education or illiterate. Only 1.5percent fathers and 0.79percent mothers have graduate degree which indicated that more than 90percent respondents are first generation of graduate among their family members in the study area.

Educational Resource

Results show that there is a crisis in availability of separate room for study, availability of computer, private tuition and electric lamp. Only stationary (96percent), books (61percent) and study chair & table (42percent) were available to the respondents. Hence, 60percent of the total respondents were deprived to availed educational resource and facilities during their higher education. All these educational resources are directly related to wealth of the family (Appendix-3a).

Workforce Participation

There were 60percent of the total respondents who were not engaged in workforce participation of any form and were devoting their full time to studies. While on the hand, total 40percent of the respondents were engaged in earning while learning in higher education. Among the working students, 17.90percent, 15.50percent and 1.2percent of the total were engaged in work as a daily wage labour, agriculture labour, and worker in private companies respectively. Further, 1.2percent was self-employed and 4.4percent was private tutors. Hence, it reveals that about one third respondents were engaged in such a works which is detrimental to access to their higher education (Appendix-3b).

Employment of Head of the Household

Approximately, 10percentrespondents belongto those family whose heads were non-working and 65percentheads of households were engaged in primary economic activities like agricultural labour, agriculture and wage labour etc. A significant proportion (21percent) of the head of the family were engaged in public sector job or retired from public job. A small proportion with 3percent of the total head of the surveyed families were in private jobs. Data analysis reveals that more than two third of heads of surveyed SCs households were engaged in primary economic activitties which is considered as low income generation sector (Appendix-3c).

Per Capita Income

Appendix-3dshows the lowest income category with earnings of \$ 1.25 US per day per person (Chen & Martin, 2008) constitute 80.55 percentof the total surveyed households whose per capita income is less than Rs. 1560 per month. Second important group of families which constitute 13.89 percentof total households have a per capita income between Rs. 1,560-3,120 per month. Rest of group of income were insignificant innumbers.

Discussion

Analysis of the result reveals that a major (40percent) segment of the total SCs students are out of higher education system.Among them 25percent were eligible to enrol in higher education but unfortunately they were unable to join the higher education which indicated their socio-economic incapability to access the higher education. The gross enrolment rate in higher education for SCs was much lower (21percent) than the general population (30percent) in 2010-11(Vijayalakshmi and Annapoorani, 2013). Thus, it is clear that the dropout rates in higher educationamong SCs are higher than national average (OECD, 2014).

Female is lagging behind in higher education to their counterpart i.e. male students. Thus, there is a gender gap existing in enrollment of higher education between men and women(Raju, 2008).Usually, father or husband create hindrance in their path to access the higher education and easily do not allow them to leave the home for higher studies or work(Nath, 2014).Further, SC/ST women face difficulty to adjust with the culture and practices in the colleges. Usually, they lack peer group support and guidance. SC Females' social status is affecting their education. In addition, the parents are also not willing to provide their support to enroll them in higher education (Jagadeeswari, 2014).

About 42percent students were married having lesser opportunities to access higher education. Early marriage is a barrier to higher education especially for girls. Early marriage is due to various factors including among others, the search for economic survival, protection of young girls, peer group and family pressure, controlling female behaviour and sexuality, and socio-cultural and religious values (Bayisenge, 2002). Approximately, 9 percent respondents were married at the age of below 18 years, which may be the cause of discounting their higher education. The early marriage is the key factor for drop out girls in education because decision about marriage and education are negatively related (Nguyen and Wodoni, 2012).

More than 90percent of the respondents' family was larger than (more than 4 members) the ideal size of the household. The people living in larger family and (generally) younger households are typically poorer, especially in developing countries. It is because the poorer tend to devote a high share of their budget to rival goods such as food (Lanjouw and Ravallion, 1995). Hence, the chances of providing

better life to family member become poor in large family size. This reflects in all spheres of life of family members i.e. education level, per capita income, assets and facilities, etc.

In case of parental education, more than 90percent respondents were first generation of graduate which indicates their parents were below graduate level of education. The father's education and economic condition is an important determining factor in achieving education (Sinha, 1982) and on-going relevance of achieved parent specially father's education on their child's self-schema as they transition to higher education (Nelson, 2009). Thus, more than 90 percent respondents have lower possibility to access the higher education.

A majority (60percent) of the respondents were deprived to availed educational resource and facilities during their higher education. There is a strong wealth effect in the probability of enrollment in education (Filmer and Pritchett, 1999). Though there is no doubt that there is increase in the educational facilities for the weaker section of the society, yet there are hidden costs. This may include the purchase of textbooks, travel charges, etc. which are much more expensive than the tuition fee (Shah and Patel, 1972).

Approximately, 40percent of the respondents were engaged in earning while learning in higher education which indicates that they belong to weaker socio-economic background. Children labour force participation substantially reduces his/her chance of education (Myron, 1996). The SCs have lower enrolment rates than the forward castes. It is mainly because of higher poverty incidence among SCs. The most important determinant of post-higher secondary education appears to be the economic status of households. Students from households with vulnerable sources of income generally cannot afford to go for higher education firstly because higher education is expensive and secondly, they have to join the workforce to supplement their household income (Dubey (2008).

More than 75percent head of the respondents' families were engaged in primary economic activities or non-working which is a low income generating sector. Majority of SCs are having low literacy status which in turn causes for backwardness with illiteracy, low income, landlessness, poverty, etc. (Ravi Babu and Chandrasekarayy, 2015). Majority of SCs depends directly or indirectly on agriculture for the livelihood and their per capita income is found to be very low (Arora, and Koundal, 2014). There are a significant number of problems for SCs students studying in rural area like poverty, family problems, social hazards and problems of age factor etc. (Dodmani and Biradar 2014). The students from poor, less educated families and rural areas have less probability to complete university level of education (Pop-Eleches, 2008).

The scheduled castes are still backward in educational achievements along with increase in dropout rate also. Financial problem, guardian unconsciousness, low attendance in school/college and illiteracy of parents are responsible for this backwardness (De and Bhowmick, 2014). Majority 80.55 percent of the total surveyed households' per capita income is only 1.25 USD per day per member. The household income is also significant determining, student effect of household income on education, higher level of income being associated with higher demand for education (Dand and Brewer, 1997).

Conclusions

Scheduled Castes is an educationally backward community in India which has proved correct in the light of primary data. Socio-economic status of SCs reveals that the lack of good source of income, lack of educational resource and facilities, illiteracy or low level of parental education, lower age of marriage, larger household size, and students' workforce participation have negative impact on

accessibility to higher education among surveyed families of SCs i.e. 40percent of the total respondents were discontinued their high education. Low per capita income among surveyed families plays a vital role in access to higher education because all other factors are directly or indirectly related with it. In terms of gender, female students are lagging behind to their counterpart in higher education. Thus it can be said that the socio-economic condition of SCs family are not suitable for support to their higher education. Therefore, there is a need of reform and proper implementation of government schemes and programmes for the educational development of deprived section of the society.

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Appendix-1				
Status of the Student in Higher Education				
District	Do not join the HE	Discontinue to HE	Continue HE	Completed HE
Cases	26	20	80	40
Faizabad	15.66%	12.05%	48.19%	24.10%
Cases	66	30	40	30
Sonbhadra	39.76%	18.07%	24.10%	18.07%
Cases	35	24	63	50
Lucknow	20.35%	13.95%	36.63%	29.07%
Total cases	127	74	183	120
Percent	25.20%	14.68%	36.31%	23.81%

Source: Computed from Household Field Work Data, 2011,

Total Number of Samples: 504

Time period: January to May 2011

Appendix-2a						
	Sex		Marital Status		Age at Effective Marriage (AEM)	
	Male	Female	Unmarried	Married	AEM < 18 Yrs	AEM 18-25 Yrs
Cases	282	222	293	211	47	164
Percent	56.0%	44.0%	59.72%	40.27%	9.30%	32.50%

Appendix-2b				
Size of the Household				
	Up to 4 member	5 to 6 person	7- 10 person	> 11person
Cases	27	145	221	111
Percent	5.40%	28.80%	43.80%	22.10%

Appendix-2c							
Educational Status of Student's Father							
	Illiterate	Primary	Junior High School	High School	12 th	Graduate	P.G.& Above
Cases	184	49	101	44	71	47	8
Percent	36.50%	9.72%	20.03%	8.73%	14.08%	9.32	1.58%

Appendix-2d							
Educational Status of Student's Mother							
	Illiterate	Primary	Junior High School	High School	12 th Class	Graduate	P.G.& Above
Cases	434	19	33	8	6	4	0
Percent	86.11%	3.76%	6.54%	1.58%	1.19%	0.79%	0.0%

Source: Computed from Household Field Work Data, 2011,

Total Number of Samples: 504

Time period: January to May 2011

Appendix-3a							
Availability of Educational Resource, Facilities and Assets in Household							
	Separate Room	Chair & Table	Electric Lamp	Stationary	Books	Computer	Private tuition
Cases	29	214	131	484	310	9	9
Percent	5.80%	42.5%	26.00%	96.00%	61.5%	1.8%	1.8%

Appendix-3b							
Workforce Participation and Type of Work done By Student							
	Non-Working	Working	Wage Labor	Primary Economic Activities	Private Work	Self employed	Tuition
Cases	302	202	90	78	6	6	22
Percent	59.92%	40.07%	17.90%	15.50%	1.20%	1.20%	4.40%

Appendix-3c				
Employment of Head of Household				
	No Working	Primary Economic Activities	Private Job	Public & Retired
Cases	54	328	16	106
Percent	10.71%	65.07%	3.17%	21.03%

Appendix-3d					
Per Capita Income of the Family					
	< Rs.1560 Per Month	Rs. 1560-3120 Per Month	Rs.3120-4680 Per Month	Rs.4680-6240 Per Month	> Rs.6240 Per Month
Cases	408	70	12	11	3
Percent	80.95%	13.89%	2.38%	2.18%	0.60%

Source: Computed from Household Field Work Data, 2011,

Total Number of Samples: 504

Time period: January to May 2011